

EFFECT OF RESIDUAL STRESSES ON THE
FRACTURE OF THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

This paper presents the results of an investigation on the first-ply failure and subsequent final failure of AS4/PEEK laminates. The laminates considered in this paper are $[0_2/90_2]_{2S}$, $[0_4/90_4]_S$, $[\pm 30_2/90_2]_S$, and $[\pm 30_4/90/90]_S$. Experimental procedures for determination of the onset of the first-ply failure and the stress-free temperature in calculation of the residual stresses are described. The experimental results compared very well with analytical predictions when the curing residual stresses are included, except for the final failure of the laminates containing no 0-degree plies. In these laminates the delamination appears to be mainly responsible for the premature failure.

KEYWORDS: Graphite Fiber; Thermoplastic; Residual Stress; First-Ply Failure; Delamination.

1. INTRODUCTION

Fiber-reinforced thermoplastic matrix composites have undergone considerable evaluation due to the interest shown by the aerospace industry. Thermoplastic composites generally show good damage resistance due primarily to their toughness. Very little investigation has been reported on the failure and damage behavior under static loading. The nature of ply failure and delamination appears to be very different from that of the state-of-the-art epoxy matrix composites. Because of high processing temperature coupled with the large thermal expansion mismatch between fiber and matrix, the resulting residual stresses could be large enough to cause premature ply cracking in a multidirectional laminate. The main objective of this study is the experimental determination of the first-ply failure and comparison with the analytical prediction. The material system chosen for this study is AS4/PEEK. The residual stress-free temperature is determined by a ply separation technique developed for this study. Residual stresses in each ply within a laminate are calculated on the basis of the temperature determined and used for the subsequent calculation of failure prediction.

The quadratic failure theory of Tsai-Wu is employed for the failure prediction study (1). Acoustic emission and microscopic techniques were employed to determine onset of the first-ply failure stress and delamination stress. The experimental data compared very well with the analytical predictions on the first-ply failure and ultimate failure. Premature ultimate failure is observed in those laminates which are delaminated and contain no 0-degree ply.

2. ANALYTICAL BACKGROUND

The constitutive equation for a ply in a symmetric multidirectional laminate due to residual stresses can be written as [2]

$$\sigma_i^R = Q_{ij}(\epsilon_i^N - e_j) \quad (1)$$

where

- Q_{ij} = reduced stiffness at the final temperature,
- ϵ_i^N = laminate thermal strains measured from the stress-free state, and
- e_j = ply thermal strains measured from the stress-free state.

The laminate thermal strains then follow from the classical laminate plate theory as

$$\epsilon_j^N = a_{ij} \int Q_{ij} \alpha_k dz (T - T_0) \quad (2)$$

where

- a_{ij} = compliance matrix at the final temperature of interest,
- α_k = coefficient of thermal expansion of a ply, and
- T and T_0 = stress-free temperature and final temperature, respectively.

Thermal strain of a ply is given by

$$e_j = \alpha_j (T - T_0) \quad (3)$$

From equations (2) and (3), the residual stress-free temperature is then given

$$T = T_0 + \frac{\epsilon_j^N - e_j}{a_{ij} \int Q_{ij} \alpha_k dz - \alpha_j} \quad (4)$$

which can be determined by measuring the residual strain ($\epsilon_j^N - e_j$) for a ply in a laminate. The ply stress is related to the applied laminate stress resultants, N_k and the curing residual stresses, σ_i^R , and given by

$$\sigma_i = a_{ij} Q_{jk} N_k + \sigma_i^R \quad (5)$$

The applied stress at the first-ply failure can be calculated using the Tsai-Wu failure theory

$$F_{ij}\sigma_j + F_i\sigma_i = 1 \quad (6)$$

where F's are strength parameters.

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The material system used in this study was AS4/PEEK supplied in prepreg form by Imperial Chemical Industries. The following types of laminates were fabricated in a hot press according to the manufacturer's recommended cure cycle: $[90_{10}/0_5/90_{10}]_T$, $[90_7/0_{14}/90_7]_T$, $[0_2/90_2]_{2S}$, $[0_4/90_4]_S$, $[\pm 30_2/90_2]_S$, and $[\pm 30_4/90_{\bar{90}}]_S$. The first two laminates were used for determining the residual stress-free temperature by measuring the curing residual strain. Axial and transverse strain gages were mounted on a flat surface of the laminate and connected to a strain indicator. The strain is taken before and after separation of the outer 0-degree plies from the laminate as shown in Figure 1. The significance of this method provides the direct measurement of the ply residual strains in a laminate. The rest of the laminates were used to investigate first-ply failure under uniaxial tensile load. All specimens were 7.62 cm long in gage section and 2 cm wide. Both side edges of the specimen were ground with sandpaper and then polished with 5 and 0.5 micron polishing powder in order to facilitate microscopic examinations. Strain gage and acoustic emission techniques were employed to determine the first-ply failure stress under uniaxial tensile loading. Physical Acoustics' Logan AT acoustic emission system was used, and the total system gain and frequency band were at 80 db and 0.1-0.3 MHz, respectively. All specimens were tested on a MTS testing machine with hydraulic grips. The specimen was unloaded and examined on a microscope after the first acoustic event occurred. After confirming the ply crack with the use of a microscope, the specimen was then loaded to final failure.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The residual strains in both longitudinal and transverse directions determined by experiment are shown in Table 1. The negative sign in the table denotes the compressive strain. The result of the epoxy matrix with the same fibers is also shown for comparison purposes. The cure temperature is 176°C for epoxy matrix composites and 382°C for PEEK composites. The experimental values are based on an average of three to five specimens per laminate.

For analysis, the following thermoelastic properties of a unidirectional ply are utilized: $E_L = 130$ GPa, $E_T = 11$ GPa, $G_{LT} = 5.7$ GPa, $\nu_{LT} = 0.3$, $\alpha_L = -0.4 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$, $\alpha_T = 30 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$, $X = 2,100$ MPa, $Y = 100$ MPa, and $S = 150$ MPa. E , G , and ν are Young's modulus, shear modulus, and Poisson's ratio, respectively. α is the coefficient of thermal expansion, and subscripts L and T denote longitudinal and transverse directions, respectively. X , Y , and S are longitudinal, transverse, and shear strength, respectively.

The elastic constants are room temperature values and determined by a separate test. The residual stress-free temperature is calculated from Equation 4 using the residual strain data (Table 1) in the

transverse direction for the unidirectional ply. The results are plotted in Figure 2. The symbols and the dotted line represent each data point and its average value. The average of the curing residual stress-free temperature is found to be 310°C with a coefficient of variation of 6.2% and is lower than the processing temperature of 382°C. The residual strain measured in Figure 2 consists of an elastic strain and time-dependent strain. The time-dependent strain is in the range of 0.015 to 0.025% in this case. It took about 50 hours to level off.

Photomicrographs of typical cracks in the 90-degree plies are presented in Figure 3(a) for the $[0_4/90_4]_S$ laminate. Unlike the epoxy matrix composite, the initial ply cracks are very small and do not cover the entire width or the entire ply thickness. It was observed that the most transverse cracks take the path along the interface between fiber and matrix, rather than the path in the matrix as seen in brittle epoxy composites. These small cracks made the acoustic emission technique difficult to use in the detection of the onset of ply cracking. The acoustic emission output signals from these small cracks are, in many cases, so small that they are difficult to distinguish from other noise at the onset of ply cracking. Because of this difficulty and the uncertainty of the acoustic signal, the specimens were initially loaded to the level just below where the first-ply failure stress was expected to occur. They were then removed from the load frame for microscopic examination. This step was repeated with a small incremental loading of 15 MPa until the first-ply crack was observed. As the applied load is increased after first-ply failure, the crack grows in a steady manner. Figure 3(b) shows the crack growth in the 90-degree ply in the $[0_4/90_4]_S$ laminate. By increasing the applied stress from 403 MPa to 561 MPa, the crack does not complete its growth; that is, the crack has not grown through the entire thickness of the eight 90-degree plies. Some cracks remained stationary (no crack growth) up to near final failure. The total number of cracks in the 90-degree plies along the entire gage length of the specimen (10 cm) is approximately 10 at the stress level of 95% of the ultimate strength.

Table 2 shows a comparison between analysis and experiment for the laminates tested at room temperature. The laminated plate theory accurately predicts the elastic constants as expected. The stress-strain curve is essentially linear up to final failure for all the laminates considered in this work as shown in Figures 4 through 7. The calculated stress level at the onset of ply cracks in all cases compares very well with the experimental results when the residual curing stresses are considered. The residual stress-free temperature determined appears to be very reasonable. It should be noted that the ply failure almost simultaneously occurred in the outer two 90-degree layers and the inner four 90-degree layers in the $[0_2/90_2]_{2S}$ laminate. The effect of layer thickness and degree of constraint does not appear to be remarkable in the tough thermoplastic composites.

In the ultimate strength tests, the results compared very well with the calculation for the cross-ply laminates. However in the $[\pm 30_2/90_2]_{2S}$ and $[\pm 30_4/90/90]_S$ laminates, the experimentally-determined strengths are much smaller than the calculation. The major reason for this difference is due to the delamination which occurred prior to ultimate failure. It is interesting to note that the delamination occurs and propagates immediately through the width in a very unstable manner. This

is really unexpected for a tough matrix system. Further work needs to be done in order to understand this unstable delamination crack growth. No thickness effect has been observed for the thickness considered in this work that is seen in the brittle epoxy matrix composites.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Experimental results indicated that the first-ply failure can be accurately predicted using classical laminated plate theory including the residual curing stresses in conjunction with the Tsai-Wu failure theory. The residual stress-free temperature was calculated from the residual strain determined by a ply separation technique. The first-ply crack is so small that it is very difficult to detect using the acoustic emission and strain gage techniques. The stress-free temperature is lower than the cure temperature. Free-edge delamination reduces the ultimate strength significantly for the laminates having no 0-degree ply.

6. REFERENCES

1. S. W. Tsai and E. Wu, "A General Theory of Strength for Anisotropic Materials," J. Compos. Mater., 5 (1971) 58.
2. N. J. Pagano and H. T. Hahn, "Evaluation of Composite Curing Stresses," ASTM-STP-617 (1977) 317.

TABLE 1. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS OF RESIDUAL STRAINS

MATERIAL	LAMINATE	$\epsilon_x, \times 10^{-6}$	$\epsilon_y, \times 10^{-6}$
AS4/PEEK	[90 ₇ /0 ₁₄ /90 ₇]T	770	-6,840
	[90 ₁₀ /0 ₅ /90 ₁₀]T	330	-6,470
AS4/3501-2	[90 ₄ /0 ₈ /90 ₄]T	420	-2,680
	[90 ₄ /0 ₄ /90 ₄]T	250	-2,180

TABLE 2. COMPARISON OF PREDICTION AND EXPERIMENT

LAMINATE	CALCULATION						EXPERIMENT			
	$\Delta T = -288^\circ\text{C}$				$\Delta T = 0$					
	E(L) GPa	ν (LT)	σ (FPF) MPa	σ (U) MPa	σ (FPF) MPa	σ (U) MPa	E(L) GPa	ν (LT)	σ (FPF) MPa	σ (U) MPa
$[0_2/90_2/0_2/90_2]_S$	69.8	0.04	225	940	770	1110	71.2	0.04	270	1000
$[0_4/90_4]_S$	69.8	0.04	225	940	770	1110	68.9	0.05	240	9333
$[\pm 30_2/90_2]_S$	51.3	0.29	150	625	510	840	51.0	0.30	126	460
$[\pm 30_4/90/90]_S$	57.4	0.55	115	735	505	835	58.2	0.59	120	555

Figure 1. Illustration of ply separation technique for measuring residual strains.

Figure 2. Experimental data for determination of the residual stress-free temperature.

(a) Applied Stress 403 MPa

(b) Applied Stress 561 MPa

Figure 3. Microphotographs showing transverse crack growth in the $[0_4/90_4]_S$ laminate.

Figure 4. Stress-strain curve for the [0₂/90₂]_{2s} laminate.

Figure 5. Stress-strain curve for the [0₄/90₄]_s laminate.

Figure 6. Stress-strain curve for the $[30_2/-30_2/90_2]_s$ laminate.

Figure 7. Stress-strain curve for the $[30_4/-30_4/90_2]_s$ laminate.

